

Open Science Opportunities for Missions and Observatories

Practical Choices to Shape Your Observing Adventure

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Appendix

This appendix presents a wealth of potential tasks to incorporate Open Science practices into a mission’s activities. These activities are roughly divided into three mission phases - the pre-proposal phase, the pre-launch phase, and the post-launch phase - with further divisions into culture and artifact related tasks. The list of tasks in a given mission phase does not repeat those listed in earlier phases even though the earlier tasks may still be relevant, and missions can choose to complete a given task related to any mission phase regardless of the current mission status. For example, the task “create a PID for the mission” is listed in the pre-launch phase, but it could be completed in the post-launch phase if not completed earlier or even in the pre-proposal phase if so desired. The motivation for including each task is included, along with a starting point on how to complete that task.

We do not consider this list of activities to be exhaustive. In fact, many recommendations in this section are related to the NASA / USA mission process, but we hope the structure and the recommendations are useful, even outside the US-centric view. The ideas for several of these stem from the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) principles for data¹ and research software, including existing standards in those areas (e.g., the many outcomes from the Research Data Alliance² and the Research Software Alliance³) (Barker et al. 2022). If you think of additional activities, please add them to the earliest relevant mission phase and category using the suggestion mode on the document. Please make sure the suggested activity is not already represented in the list before adding it.

Link to the main living document: <https://tinyurl.com/OpenScienceMissions>

¹ <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>

² <https://www.rd-alliance.org/>

³ <https://www.researchsoft.org/>

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Pre-Proposal Phase

For missions funded by NASA, the OSDMP is required as part of the proposal for competed missions and at the Preliminary Design Review stage for directed missions. Tasks in this pre-proposal section refer to potential items that could be incorporated into the proposal and mission work at that stage or earlier, although many of these tasks can be added in any mission phase.

Mission Artifacts

List of tasks:

1. Create a persistent identifier such as a Digital Object Identifier⁴ (DOI) via DataCite for the mission (once that is possible) and all instruments.
2. Cite the mission PID and related instruments in all mission products.
3. Create and update research plans (preregistrations) on OSF with DOIs⁵.
4. Prepare to obtain a CC0 license or similar for the data and an open license for the software (as possible).
5. Share sample or modeled datasets in a public repository with a DOI.
6. Find and collaborate with existing open source software efforts to plan out algorithm needs.
7. Work through possible legal limitations, such as licensing and permissions, for research plans, datasets, and software to be able to be developed and shared openly.
8. Plan how to preserve and share slide decks, posters, and similar material from all meetings from a single publicly accessible location (e.g., Zenodo collection or OSF Meetings).
9. Plan to archive mission data and related artifacts at domain-specific repositories.
10. Plan the development approach and release method for mission software.
11. Include all completed items in your proposal's OSDMP or similar document.

⁴ <https://www.doi.org/>

⁵ <https://osf.io/>

Task Descriptions:

1. Create a persistent identifier such as a Digital Object Identifier⁶ (DOI) via DataCite for the mission (once that is possible) and all instruments.
 - a. **Why:** Creating a PIDs such as a DOI for the mission and its instruments provides a way to interconnect all of the artifacts from a mission. This improves how easy it is to discover publications, datasets, software, people, instruments, and other items that become associated with the mission over time. Ideally, missions will also create DOIs for each instrument to distinguish when artifacts are related to a specified instrument. This increases the number of pathways for the public to discover and learn more about your mission, which in turn can result in a greater number of citations. Creating this PID for the mission separately from the main mission publication allows for a richer interconnection between all of the entities, including as those connections change with time, than is possible with a static publication. Also, if the mission is not funded, this identifier can be used to protect the various components of the planned mission by providing a way for proper attribution to occur in publications and later proposals.
 - b. **How:** NASA SMD data repositories can assist missions in this work by using their DataCite subscriptions. Typically, the basic metadata to include for the mission and each instrument are the name, any associated acronyms for the mission or instrument, a description, any known related artifacts (publications, software, OSDMPs, datasets, presentations, etc), people (ideally via their ORCiDs⁷), associated institutions (ideally via their RORs⁸), and so on. Depending on your science area, there may also be opportunities to use terms from a controlled vocabulary (e.g. the blue terms on this webpage⁹) to indicate various keywords. *Note:* As of the date of this publication, the correct type of PID for a mission has not yet been determined, but is likely to be a DataCite DOI based on current efforts in the Research Data Alliance¹⁰. However, DOIs have been agreed upon as the correct PID for instruments.
2. Cite the mission PID and related instruments in all mission products.
 - a. **Why:** Citing the persistent identifier for the mission, usually a DOI, links all of the mission products and related entities to the mission. This increases the number of pathways for the community to discover the mission.
 - b. **How:** Cite the mission's PID as you would any other item. For instance, the mission PID can be included on a Zenodo¹¹ submission in the related identifier section.
3. Create and update research plans (preregistrations) on OSF with DOIs¹².
 - a. **Why:** A research plan is basically an outline of why a given science question is important, how the mission data will be used to answer that question, what other

⁶ <https://www.doi.org/>

⁷ <https://orcid.org/>

⁸ <https://ror.org/>

⁹ <https://osdr.nasa.gov/bio/repo/data/studies/OSD-516>

¹⁰ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/persistent-identification-instruments-wg/activity/>

¹¹ <https://zenodo.org/>

¹² <https://osf.io/>

artifacts (e.g. data, software, etc) are expected to be needed, and the analysis processes intended to be used in that analysis. Posting a research plan on a version-controlled platform, whether initially public or private, allows the researchers to track what works and what doesn't work across the different versions as they explore the relevant science and processes. Making that research plan public with the publication of the result allows others to see what worked and what didn't, which can make others' research more efficient and often initiates collaborations.

- b. **How:** Most of the material in a research plan can be sourced from a proposal. Usually, more detail is included and added as the work progresses. Other sciences often refer to this as a preregistration for exploratory research. Our use of the idea here is to document the research process, with no particular focus on a registered report as done in those fields. See Pariente et al. (2022) for a discussion on this topic.
4. Prepare to obtain a CC0 license or similar for the data and an open license for the software (as possible).
 - a. **Why:** Choosing an open license for the data, software, and other artifacts produced by the mission allows their users the most freedom in using those items. The CC0 license is the most open license for data and is the license of choice for NASA-funded data. Commonly used open licenses for software include BSD, Apache, and MIT¹³. See the Open Source Initiatives Proliferation Report¹⁴ for a list of the nine licenses commonly used in the community.
 - b. **How:** Generally, licensing data or software must be done through a defined process involving the legal department at the institution creating the artifact. An easy way to avoid complications in the licensing process is to indicate the license to be used for each artifact in the proposal which the institution then approves. An additional approach is to obtain a license for an empty public repository and afterwards develop the code on that repository.
5. Share sample or modeled datasets in a public repository with a DOI.
 - a. **Why:** Sharing these datasets before the launch of a mission helps the community understand what types of science questions may be answerable by the mission's data, potentially even beyond the science questions the mission includes in its purpose. This practice also helps the community become familiar with the data. At later stages, sharing these data can help potential contributors to the mission software analysis tools understand what modifications are needed compared to the actual data. This can be particularly important when community contributions are allowed on mission software, including incorporating mission software into other software packages.
 - b. **How:** All data produced by missions funded by the NASA Science Mission Directorate (SMD) are required to be archived at a designated NASA SMD data repository. Contact your assigned repository for information on this process.

¹³ <https://spdx.org/licenses/>

¹⁴ <https://opensource.org/proliferation-report>

6. Find and collaborate with existing open source software efforts to plan out algorithm needs.
 - a. **Why:** There are already quite a large variety of software packages that address the various needs for a mission. In some cases, it is easier to adapt an existing software solution to work for a new mission rather than reinvent that work. In other cases, the software needed for a mission can be built on pieces that already exist. Searching for existing software to build on or adapt, such as using software search interfaces or asking around at conferences with software-related sessions, often results in less effort from the mission. Additionally, this demonstrates a collaborative stance with the software community.
 - b. **How:** Relevant software can be hard to find, especially given the current lack of software discovery tools. A good place to start is at a general conference that covers several sciences, such as AGU, particularly looking for sessions focused on software or on missions. Connect with people in those sessions, even if they are focused on a completely different science, and ask them what they use for a given software task, such as extracting data from CCSDS packets, or if a given type of analysis is already possible or almost possible in their package. Follow through with these contacts to work out whether adoption, adaption, or new work is needed. Include the result of that investigative work in your OSDMP's software section.
7. Work through possible legal limitations, such as licensing and permissions, for research plans, datasets, and software to be able to be developed and shared openly.
 - a. **Why:** It is easier to incorporate the intended license for each item into the mission's OSDMP, with the hosting institution's approval, rather than at a later stage. Attempting to assign a license not mentioned in the OSDMP to a particular item at a later date is not always successful and can be an extremely long and time-intensive process.
 - b. **How:** Specify the license to be assigned to each data product, software item, and publication (including research plans, if relevant, and conference presentations) in the mission OSDMP, then obtain your institution's approval of the OSDMP. Usually, this results in a much smoother release process of those items.
8. Plan how to preserve and share slide decks, posters, and similar material from all meetings from a single publicly accessible location (e.g., Zenodo collection or OSF Meetings).
 - a. **Why:** Centralizing the location of all mission publications, presentations, posters, and similar material makes it easier for others to find these items, especially items that are not peer-reviewed. Ideally, the link to the landing page with these items listed will be included in the related identifiers of the mission's landing page associated with its PID and in the description.
 - b. **How:** Several free and easy options are available for this. One option is to create a Zenodo community¹⁵. Publications, presentations, posters, research plans, and similar items can be submitted to the mission's Zenodo community¹⁶. Another

¹⁵ <https://zenodo.org/communities>

¹⁶ E.g. <https://zenodo.org/communities/2024softwareforthenasasmworkshop/records>

similar option is OSF Meetings¹⁷, which can be used in a similar way for missions.

9. Plan to archive mission data and related artifacts at domain-specific repositories.
 - a. **Why:** Domain-specific repositories are funded to preserve the submitted artifacts, including access to those objects as technology changes over the decades. Submitting the mission artifacts to these repositories can be a complex process, but with the significant benefit of ensuring access and increasing the usability of those items long term. Such a submission is often required for missions.
 - b. **How:** Contact the domain-specific repository in your science area and follow their instructions on how to submit the various artifacts. A growing number of repositories have different levels of requirements, each associated with different services to be provided at each level. Generally, a greater number of requirements results in a greater number of services to be performed in support of the artifacts, such as requiring more substantive documentation and links to software and publication DOIs at higher levels. Missions can negotiate with the domain-specific repositories to select a level that can be supported by the mission funding and has the repository's agreement. Include the agreed upon level of service for each expected mission artifact in the mission's OSDMP, including the agreed upon delivery method (e.g. per major version or continuous).
10. Plan the development approach and release method for mission software.
 - a. **Why:** For many missions, the details of the development and release of mission software are secondary to the mission science. However, not planning for and including such details in the OSDMP can cause significant delays or expensive legal barriers later. Make sure to prepare for open development of unrestricted mission software.
 - b. **How:** Determine what software components are expected to be unrestricted or restricted and indicate this in the OSDMP. If any collaborations with existing open-source software packages are worthwhile, indicate those collaborations on the OSDMP even if not finalized, including the name of the software package, the expected point of contact on both sides for the collaboration, the main functionality to be developed in support of the mission via that collaboration, and the expected benefits (e.g. added functionality for the wider public, contributions to open-source software, etc). Determine how often the mission software will be released and indicate this on the OSDMP. A few important components are
 - i. The cadence of the major releases,
 - ii. The availability of those releases (e.g. public vs internal),
 - iii. The minting of DOIs for those releases,
 - iv. The completeness of the documentation,
 - v. The code coverage requirements,
 - vi. Level of effort planned to manage community contributions, and
 - vii. Details concerning the alignment of that software with community standards.

¹⁷ <https://help.osf.io/article/397-osf-meetings>

An ideal example for mission software in Heliophysics: *New major releases of mission software will be made publicly available via GitHub with mature executable documentation with sample mission data supported by a public HelioCloud instance every 8 months following the initial release. DOIs will be minted for each release through the established GitHub-Zenodo workflow. 0.25 FTE of one software developer will be devoted to manage any community contributions deemed useful with a decision workflow to be established and made public. Mission software will be required to have at least 80% code coverage as determined by an existing analysis tool before a major release is created. The unrestricted portion of this software will be aligned with the relevant requirements of the silver tier of the Python in Heliophysics Community. A review of the mission software will be completed through either pyOpenSci or the Journal of Open Source Software within 2 years of the initial software release.* Additional information will likely be needed on the OSDMP for your mission's software. Please check those guidelines for details.

11. Include all completed items in your proposal's OSDMP or similar document.
 - a. **Why:** This is what this paper is all about! The more Open Science activities that can be included in the OSDMP with some brief comments about their impact, the more competitive the OSDMP will be when reviewed.
 - b. **How:** As you work through each section of the OSDMP, check this list for relevant items to include in that section. Tasks related to mission artifacts will most likely fit in those sections. Tasks related to mission culture will most likely fit in a general Open Science activities section. Make sure to not only include the activity, but to explain how including that activity will increase the expected impact of the mission on the science and the community.

Mission Culture

List of Tasks:

1. Fund team leaders and members to become familiar with the practices of open science, such as by completing all five of NASA's Open Science 101 training modules.
2. Discuss ways to incorporate open science practices in all mission aspects.
3. Draft an open science plan for your mission.
4. Appoint team members to be responsible for guiding open science practices.
5. Recognize open science activities in hiring practices.
6. Construct a code of conduct and collaboration rules or contributor guidelines.
7. Define what activities will be open to non team members and indicate publicly.
8. Determine how to track community contributions and make the tracking public.
9. Define a clear way for potential collaborators to contact mission and science working group leaders.
10. Create a website for the mission.
11. Sign the Declaration on Research Assessment statement.

Task Descriptions:

1. Fund team leaders and members to become familiar with the practices of open science, such as by completing all five of NASA's Open Science 101 training modules.
 - a. **Why:** It is hard to understand how to incorporate Open Science practices when no one on the mission is familiar with them. Having one person on the mission team complete some form of training on this topic will help the mission incorporate Open Science practices in a productive and positive manner. This also signals a potential level of commitment to the ideas of Open Science in addition to the practices included on the OSDMP.
 - b. **How:** Ask at least one mission team member to complete training on Open Science and ensure that person does so. Ideally, this team member would be in a leadership position on the team. The NASA Open Science 101 course¹⁸ is a great choice, even if the team member only has time to complete the Ethos of Open Science training.
2. Discuss ways to incorporate open science practices in all mission aspects.
 - a. **Why:** Having these discussions across the many types of participants in the mission provides a way to harness their different ways of thinking to help the mission increase its impact on the community.
 - b. **How:** Schedule a virtual mini-workshop (usually ~2 hours long) with all members of and contributors to the mission. Begin with a short opening presentation describing the purpose of the mini-workshop - to brainstorm ways to incorporate Open Science practices into the mission. Provide an anonymous way for everyone to contribute their ideas during the presentations (e.g. a Slido¹⁹, Padlet²⁰, or Miro board²¹) and include a short link and QR code to that method in the opening presentation. Continue the workshop with an introductory presentation to Open Science, followed by a presentation on the mission components and plans. Once the presentations are done, show those ideas and allow for discussion to take place. Usually, this discussion is allotted for half of the workshop time. It is often helpful to come up with discussion questions beforehand to get the discussion started. These discussions can begin with the tasks laid out in this paper, if desired, and will likely result in new ideas or custom ways to implement Open Science practices for the mission. The ideas generated in this mini-workshop should be discussed in the mission leadership to decide what ideas to include moving forward. Those decisions should be communicated to all on the mission team.
3. Draft an open science plan for your mission.
 - a. **Why:** It is good to have a list of Open Science practices the mission will incorporate. It is better to have a plan on how and when those practices will be executed. Having a reasonably detailed plan on how and when each Open Science practice will be executed during the mission demonstrates an increased level of commitment to Open Science. This plan could be made public (e.g. on

¹⁸ <https://science.nasa.gov/open-science/training/>

¹⁹ <https://www.slido.com/>

²⁰ <https://padlet.com/>

²¹ <https://miro.com/>

- a. **Why:** It is not useful to say that a mission is interested in collaborating with members of the community and not provide a defined way to contact them. However, there should be some protection from spam emails.
 - b. **How:** One easy way to do this is to have a platform for communication other than email. This could be a Discourse²⁷, a Slack channel²⁸, a GitHub repository²⁹ with the Issues and Discussion features activated, or a project page on the OSF³⁰. Currently, the Discourse and Slack features have associated charges, but the GitHub and OSF options are free. Another method is to include a contact form on the mission webpage with some filtering method behind the scenes to direct the message to the relevant person. The chosen platform should be linked in a prominent way from the main mission page.
10. Create a website for the mission.
- a. **Why:** A website for the mission provides a central location for the community to find information about the mission, including how to contribute, how to contact the right person, what conferences the mission staff are involved in, and artifacts generated by the mission (e.g. links to any open software repositories for the mission, DOIs for conference presentations, sample datasets, peer-reviewed publications, and so on).
 - b. **How:** At a very high level, any SMD-funded mission, regardless of who's leading it, must create its public-facing website on the science website^{31,32}. A mission website can be as simple as a wiki page, or as mature as a nicely designed modern website. The approach should be chosen with some care based on the funding available and the functionality required. Some important components to include are:
 - i. A description of the mission,
 - ii. Associated acronyms for the mission,
 - iii. A list of people on the mission team, including contributors from the community, (with their ORCID) and their associated institutions (with their RORs),
 - iv. Links to various mission artifacts that are publicly available (e.g. conference presentations, peer-reviewed publications, the OSDMP, sample datasets, and the mission and instrument metadata records) ideally via their PIDs (typically DOIs),
 - v. How to contact mission team members,

²⁷ <https://www.discourse.org/>

²⁸ <https://slack.com/>

²⁹ <https://github.com/>

³⁰ <https://osf.io/>

³¹ <https://science.nasa.gov/science-missions/>

³² NASA Interim Directive (NID): Public Web Experience:
https://nodis3.gsfc.nasa.gov/OPD_Docs/NID_2800_147_.pdf

NASA Advisory Implementing Instructions (NAII):

https://nodis3.gsfc.nasa.gov/OPD_Docs/NAII_2800_2_.pdf

- vi. Links to ongoing work, such as active GitHub repositories and Zenodo communities, and related items (e.g. code of conduct, collaboration rules, Open Science plans),
 - vii. What major conferences the mission's work will be presented in the near future, and
 - viii. Any other information the mission is willing to make public that is of use to the community.
11. Sign the Declaration on Research Assessment statement.
- a. **Why:** Signing the DORA statement signifies that the mission is interested in promoting best practices in the assessment of researchers and scholarly research. The DORA statement discourages the use of journal metrics as the primary assessment of a person's performance, instead emphasizing quality of research over quantity of research. That research increasingly includes dataset generation, software development, and other non-traditional contributions to a solid research product.
 - b. **How:** Navigate to the DORA website (<https://sfdora.org/>) and sign the statement as an individual. If possible, ask your institution and funding agency to also sign the statement.

Development Phase

The pre-launch phase is after the mission proposal has been funded and before the launch date of the mission. For observatories and ground-based efforts, this is after the proposal has been funded and before commissioning for the ground-based effort is completed.

Mission Artifacts

Task List:

1. Create a network of projects (e.g. one subproject per working group) using existing infrastructure.
2. Share updated sample datasets in a public repository with a DOI.
3. Collaborate with existing open source software to accelerate development.
4. Create a public code repository with a DOI for each section of software.
5. Collaborate with the public on documentation and tests for public mission software.
6. Use best practices for software development, documentation and packaging (see <https://www.pyopensci.org>)
7. Create a book of executable notebooks demonstrating various portions of the data processing, calibrations, and science analyses.
8. Preserve and share slide decks, posters, and similar material from all meetings from a single publicly accessible location (e.g. Zenodo collection, OSF Meetings, or the mission's website).
9. Create a RestAPI to serve data through (in near real-time if possible).
10. Create an LLM for the mission.

Task Descriptions:

1. Create a network of projects (e.g. one subproject per working group) using existing infrastructure.
 - a. **Why:** Separating the work for a given mission into distinct but related projects provides a central location for each project to discuss, iterate, and collaborate on the portions of the mission development assigned to each project. Hosting those efforts on existing infrastructure such as the OSF project pages or on GitHub provides a uniform interface, collaboration method, and communication pathway across the mission's projects, which simplifies involvement across projects, and provides a free developed infrastructure for that work. For the projects that can be public, this also provides a simple way to incorporate collaboration from the community in the methods specified by the mission. For some missions, a more complex system may be required³³.
 - b. **How:** First, the mission leadership will need to separate the work for the mission into several main tasks, such as development of the different types of software needed, data analysis tools development, data preparation, various science teams, and so on. Then, the appropriate team member can create the project pages. If using OSF, the organizers can create a main project page for the mission and then create separate project pages that are linked to this page for major efforts. Project components can be created for smaller efforts that are components of the larger ones. Each linked project page and component can be independently made public or private. For more information, please see the main OSF website³⁴ and some recent testing (Ringuette et al. 2023). If the mission team decides to use GitHub, a similar network of project pages can be implemented by creating a new user managed by a mission leader with multiple repositories. Each repository can be focused on a different effort and can be either public or private to the contributors based on the need for that effort. However, sub-components are more difficult to manage on GitHub since sub-repositories cannot be created. Both the OSF project pages and the GitHub repositories can be assigned DOIs individually, but the degree of integrations with external components such as online storage drives (e.g. folders on a Google drive) vary.
2. Share updated sample datasets in a public repository with a DOI.
 - a. **Why:** Sharing updates of sample datasets publicly helps the community better understand the mission evolution and potential science uses of the data that the mission may not have thought of.
 - b. **How:** Work with the appropriate data repository - HDRL for NASA-funded missions - to publish the original and updated sample datasets as soon as they

³³ E.g. the approach shown in https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/135pRcpHooV6qc2bGnO_ujq7vKqm1xx_/edit?usp=drive_link&uid=118198339287841207428&rtpof=true&sd=true, presented at the 2024 NASA SMD Data Repository Workshop in the Desirable Characteristics session.

³⁴ <https://osf.io/>

are available and notify the community through newsletters and at related conferences of the newly available datasets.

3. Collaborate with existing open source software to accelerate development.
 - a. **Why:** Missions are not required by NASA's SPD-41a to accept contributions from the community. However, collaborating with existing open source software is not only encouraged by NASA's SPD-41a, but it also has several benefits. This activity improves the software capability, outsources some of the software maintenance long-term, incorporates the mission into community software, can increase interoperability of the mission outputs with other data, and improves the chance of acquiring funding, assuming all other things are equal.
 - b. **How:** Make sure to include this in the proposal funding to ensure there is support for the work. Even if there is no funding specified for this, it is in some cases still faster to collaborate to develop a needed functionality rather than work independently. Begin by looking through software websites (e.g. PyHC for python software in Heliophysics) for existing and closely-related software packages, use the repository communication methods (e.g. Issues on GitHub) for that software package to begin the collaboration, and work out what software capabilities will best benefit from the work. In some cases, add-on funding is available for such work.
4. Create a public code repository with a DOI for each section of software.
 - a. **Why:** Creating a DOI for each section of software makes that software permanently referenceable. Make sure to update the DOI for each new major release.
 - b. **How:** First, create a repository on a public platform (e.g. GitHub³⁵). If the software is hosted on GitHub, each repository can use the existing workflow³⁶ to Zenodo to create a DOI for each major release. For the super-achievers, you can add the mission and instrument PIDs (e.g. DOIs) to the metadata record on Zenodo to link the software to the mission and its instruments.
5. Collaborate with the public on documentation and tests for public mission software.
 - a. **Why:** Although missions are not required by NASA's SPD-41a to accept contributions from the community, doing so tends to increase the final quality of the mission products. The public that is interested in the mission software is in most cases the same group that will also use the software. Including them in testing the software and improving documentation provides an often free pool of reviewers to improve and strengthen both the documentation and the software. Some contributors may also contribute tests to improve code coverage.
 - b. **How:** Host the software and documentation on a public software website that provides pull request and discussion capabilities (e.g. GitHub). Make the repository hosting these items public. Add a license, a code of conduct, and

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https://github.com/OpenScienceMOOC/Module-5-Open-Research-Software-and-Open-Source/blob/master/content_development/Task_1.md

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https://github.com/OpenScienceMOOC/Module-5-Open-Research-Software-and-Open-Source/blob/master/content_development/Task_2.md

- contributor guidelines that make clear what contributions will be accepted and how to make those contributions. Ensure that one funded member of the mission team is assigned the responsibility of managing those contributions. For contributions that are useful, collaborate with the contributors, include their work, and add their name to the software citation in the DOI creation.
6. Use best practices for software development, documentation and packaging (see <https://www.pyopensci.org>)
 - a. **Why:** Including best practices for software development makes the code easier to use, maintain, and develop, especially for people external to the mission team.
 - b. **How:** Base your software development methods on best practices from the beginning. If you already have a significant start, choose the most relevant and beneficial practices to work towards incorporating, ideally using tools to streamline the process where possible.
 7. Create a book of executable notebooks demonstrating various portions of the data processing, calibrations, and science analyses.
 - a. **Why:** Preparing executable notebooks to demonstrate how to prepare and use your mission's data greatly decreases the chance of the data being prepared and used improperly. Hosting this capability with computational access next to the data (e.g. on the cloud hosted by the data repository) increases the openness of the data to the community. If this activity is done in addition to allowing the community to test these items, then this activity provides a stronger connection to the mission's user community and increases the community ownership of the mission products.
 - b. **How:** Prepare a software environment that is needed to perform the data preparation and analyses tasks to be represented in the notebooks. Collaborate with the data repository to create the software environment on the cloud alongside some sample mission data. Put the various steps of each task in one notebook per task type, such as one notebook for data processing, one for calibration, etc. Ensure these notebooks can be copied by cloud users and used for their own work. Maintaining these resources during the lifetime of the mission is critical to mission product users. Ideally, these resources should be archived with instructions on how to keep them executable.
 8. Preserve and share slide decks, posters, and similar material from all meetings from a single publicly accessible location (e.g. Zenodo collection, OSF Meetings, or the mission's website).
 - a. **Why:** For NASA-funded missions, SPD-41a requires these items to be made publicly accessible for public scientific meetings for which the mission is the primary sponsor, such as a yearly workshop but not including private science team meetings. In general, it benefits the community to see the status, various announcements, and explanations typically included in these materials and other publicly presented materials before the mission publication(s), even for those not able to attend the meeting. Making these items public allows those interested to stay updated on the mission status and progress.

6. Create and use an open science points system for individuals and teams to be acknowledged for their efforts and earn rewards.
7. Determine authorship order based on a public standardized rubric for contributions to publications, data and software, and including non-team members' contributions.

Task Descriptions:

1. Provide public information specifically geared towards scientists who are not on the team (non-team-members).
 - a. **Why:** Explaining mission topics and statuses without using jargon and specialized terms greatly helps make the information provided more approachable by scientists not directly associated with the mission. This is desirable to increase the community buy-in for the mission products and can also help the mission acquire extended funding if the mission is successful.
 - b. **How:** Write mission materials such as documentation, notebooks, website materials, and presentations without using jargon and specialized terms. One way to check for this is to have a graduate student in the same science area review the work and ask questions. Your answers to those questions should lead to rephrasing of the related material.
2. Host events and activities that promote collaboration with the community (open science meetings, working groups, special sessions).
 - a. **Why:** Spending the time on this task increases community buy-in for the mission, increases feedback on mission development, and, if that feedback is acted upon, can improve the mission products in significant ways.
 - b. **How:** At the simple end of the spectrum, this activity could be hosting virtual public office hours for the mission. At the complex end, this could be hosting a yearly meeting for the mission that is open to the public. Regardless of the complexity, the event(s) should be advertised broadly.
3. Communicate to the public through open access platforms (like HelioNauts, GitHub discussions, and Slack) to ensure everyone has access to knowledge and solutions.
 - a. **Why:** Purposeful communication of updates about the mission status and related items helps the community stay abreast of events of interest for the mission. Publicizing this information can also increase community participation in the mission development.
 - b. **How:** Post notices in all related newsletters and on all related platforms about significant updates to the mission status (upcoming and current) and data and software development milestones and availability. This could also be done through a mission email list.
4. Add short routine updates (e.g. every 1-2 months) on what each portion of the mission team is working on or has recently achieved (e.g. 1-2 paragraphs with a graphic or group picture).
 - a. **Why:** Providing a short update on each group's progress with pictures of those people helps the community feel included in the mission and can increase the community buy-in for the mission.

Post-Launch Phase

The post-launch phase is after the mission has launched and has completed its commissioning phase, whether in space or on the ground.

Mission Artifacts

Task List:

1. Obtain a CC0 license or similarly open license for the data and a commonly used open license for the software (as possible).
2. Develop and iterate on calibration and data processing software openly to advance mission science through collaborations with the community.
3. Update and collaborate on executable notebooks demonstrating various portions of the data processing, calibrations, and science analyses.
4. If not already built into existing open source community software, transfer the mission software into an existing open source software package for long-term availability and maintenance.
5. Create a new DOI for each software version associated with a data version, and connect the DOIs for the software and data versions in the metadata.
6. Write a publication for the software developed in support of the mission.
7. Transfer mission data and related artifacts to domain-specific repositories.
8. Conduct routine (e.g. yearly) competitions between science working groups to reproduce the other groups' work. Include the public on this via hackathons. (This work can be published!)
9. Share data statuses, processing levels, and other updates on the mission website.

Task Descriptions:

1. Obtain a CC0 license or similarly open license for the data and a commonly used open license for the software (as possible).
 - a. **Why:** Choosing an open license for the data, software, and other artifacts produced by the mission allows their users the most freedom in using those items. The CC0 license is the most open license for data and is the license of choice for NASA-funded data. The CC-BY licenses are also common for mission and observatory data products outside of the USA. Commonly used open licenses for software include BSD, Apache, and MIT⁴⁰. See the Open Source Initiatives Proliferation Report⁴¹ for a list of the nine licenses commonly used in the community.
 - b. **How:** Generally, licensing data or software must be done through a defined process involving the legal department at the institution creating the artifact. If the specific license was not indicated in the proposal, then the licensing process may be complex, especially for software. It may be possible to acquire add-on funding to perform the potential additional work needed to acquire the proper license. In

⁴⁰ <https://spdx.org/licenses/>

⁴¹ <https://opensource.org/proliferation-report>

- some cases, it may be easier to obtain a license for an empty public repository rather than one with developed code. Please coordinate with your institution.
2. Develop and iterate on calibration and data processing software openly to advance mission science through collaborations with the community.
 - a. **Why:** NASA-funded missions are required to develop their software openly on a publicly-accessible version-controlled platform that allows contributions and engagement from the community if the software is not restricted or commercial (see SPD-41a section VI. E for details), including a code of conduct and contributor guidelines. More generally, developing the calibration and data processing software openly allows the community to see how the mission development is progressing and provide them the opportunity to be more informed on the details of that work in related conversations. Ideally, this will be done in combination with allowing the community to contribute to that code. An additional benefit is that there is a copy of the code separate from the software developer(s) machines in case one or more of those machines fail.
 - b. **How:** If the software is restricted or commercial, open development could be a security risk and should not be done. If the software is not restricted or commercial, then simply create an account on a publicly-accessible version-controlled platform (e.g. GitHub), create a repository, and upload the code there. Then, add any changes to the code on regular cadence, ideally daily.
 3. Update and collaborate on executable notebooks demonstrating various portions of the data processing, calibrations, and science analyses.
 - a. **Why:** Although missions are not required by NASA's SPD-41a to accept contributions from the community, doing so tends to increase the final quality of the mission products. Including the user community in the maintenance of the mission's executable notebooks has several benefits. First, it incorporates users outside of the mission team as testers, providing feedback on the content and executability of the notebook from an external user's perspective. Second, it provides a way for more technical users to contribute potential fixes for any errors found. Problems with those suggestions are likely to point out misunderstandings of the data or software in use, which should lead to further improvements in the notebooks. Last, this activity increases community ownership of the mission and its products as with other similar collaborative activities.
 - b. **How:** Host the notebooks on a GitHub or similar repository where a code of conduct and contributor's guidelines are posted. Advertise the executable notebooks at various scientific meetings where the mission science and artifacts are presented. Mention in those advertising efforts that community contributions are welcome. When the contributions are posted, respond to them with any questions or clarifying comments. If after some discussion the contribution is not useful, explain why and ideally also explain what alternate contribution would be more useful. If the contribution is useful, then accept it with any needed edits. For reported issues, determine what priority level the issue should have and work towards resolving it, assuming the needed funding is there. Ideally, the executable notebook would be hosted on the cloud, such as on Google CoLab,

- Binder, or DeepNote. In some cases, these platforms may not be enough for sustainable notebooks and containerization may be needed.
4. If not already built into existing open source community software, transfer the mission software into an existing open source software package for long-term availability and maintenance.
 - a. **Why:** Long-term maintenance of mission-specific processing and analysis software is typically not funded with the mission. This presents problems for users once that software no longer works, decreasing the usefulness of the mission data to the science community. One approach that has worked for many missions is to collaborate with a highly-used open source software package to incorporate the mission-specific data processing and analysis routines into those packages (e.g. pySPEDAS and SunPy for Space and Solar Physics). This approach transfers the maintenance responsibility to an open-source software package in the community, lessening the burden on the mission team. This also increases the likelihood of that software package obtaining software maintenance funding.
 - b. **How:** Determine what open-source software package is highly used by the community and most relevant to the mission's science. Contact the software package leaders to collaborate on incorporating the relevant mission-specific routines into that software package, potentially through a separate funded effort. Make sure to include code tests to ensure the routines produce the correct result in the future and to reduce the use of incorrectly processed mission data in scientific research. A bonus task here is to include the software package as a related item in the mission DOI metadata and to include the mission as a related item and/or keyword in the software package's metadata.
 5. Create a new DOI for each software version associated with a data version, and connect the DOIs for the software and data versions in the metadata.
 - a. **Why:** Different versions of mission data are in many cases produced by different versions of the mission software. Additionally, the new version of the mission data may require a new version of the analysis software provided by the mission. Associating these artifacts together through distinct DOIs provides not only a clearer explanation of how the new data version was produced, but also what specific version of the analysis software should be used on that data version. This connection helps the community understand how to properly process and analyze the mission data, thus decreasing how often improperly processed and analyzed mission data is used in scientific publications.
 - b. **How:** First, if the software is hosted on GitHub, you can automate the production of a DOI for each new major release⁴². Use the zenodo.json file approach to include custom metadata for that release. DOIs for related softwares and datasets, such as the software that produced the dataset, the dataset version

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https://github.com/OpenScienceMOOC/Module-5-Open-Research-Software-and-Open-Source/blob/master/content_development/Task_2.md See also: https://tutorials.inbo.be/tutorials/git_zenodo/

produced, and so on, should be included in the “related identifiers” section⁴³. Next, include the DOIs of the related softwares in the file headers of the dataset files and in the DOI metadata of the new dataset.

6. Write a publication for the software developed in support of the mission.
 - a. **Why:** The software supporting a mission is typically quite a significant contribution to the mission, both in creating the data products the community will use and for use by that community in analyzing those data products. Writing a publication for the software provides a standard way for those that have contributed to the software development to receive credit and citations for their work.
 - b. **How:** Several journals accept publications describing software, such as the Journal of Open Source Software and some domain-specific journals, typically those dedicated to methods. These articles do not need to be long, but should introduce the software to the community, including examples of how to use it to perform the science typical for the mission.
7. Transfer mission data and related artifacts to domain-specific repositories.
 - a. **Why:** Transferring mission data to a domain-specific repository is often a required activity for the mission. This requirement may include DOIs of publicly released mission software and related documentation for higher levels of service. Regardless of whether the activity is required or not, completing this activity ensures the usefulness and accessibility of the submitted artifacts over a time much greater than the mission length. Including links to externally available related artifacts (e.g. processing and analysis software and mission publications) and quality data documentation in those submissions increases the community’s understanding of how the data was produced, how to analyze the data properly, and increases the community trust in that output.
 - b. **How:** Contact the domain-specific repository indicated in the mission’s data management plan or related document and follow their instructions on how to submit the various artifacts in alignment with the service level indicated in the OSDMP for each artifact.
8. Conduct routine (e.g. yearly) competitions between science working groups to reproduce the other groups’ work. Include the public on this via hackathons. (This work can be published!)
 - a. **Why:** This activity provides the most thorough test of the science conclusions in mission publications, including monitoring any potential changes needed in those conclusions as new data versions are released. Conducting these replication efforts externally with the mission’s user community increases their participation in the mission science and greatly increases community trust in the mission science. If advertised in broad ways, it can also increase involvement and opportunities for early-career researchers both with the mission and its users and with Open Science practices.

⁴³ <https://github.com/zenodraft/metadata-schema-zenodo/> , <https://stackoverflow.com/questions/57427477/how-to-template-zenodo-auto-release-archive> and <https://developers.zenodo.org/#github>

- b. **How:** Document the analysis process used to produce each main science conclusion for the mission, ideally in an executable notebook for greatest ease. Put this detailed description or notebook on a public repository after the publication is released with links to the exact software and mission data version the analysis requires. After several months or a year has passed, host a meeting for the mission, possibly as an add-on day to an existing workshop, and dedicate several hours or more for the attendees to attempt to replicate the science result. Publish the results of the effort in the workshop report and preferably also in a separate, more detailed publication. The Center for Open Science is an excellent resource in this area⁴⁴ and can guide those interested in good ways to perform this activity.
9. Share data statuses, processing levels, and other updates on the mission website.
 - a. **Why:** Sharing statuses, basic information about the datasets, and other relevant updates even after the mission has ended maintains communication with the mission user community.
 - b. **How:** This can be as simple as adding update messages to the top of the mission website. Missions can also add these notifications to various conference presentations to help broadcast updates. In addition to the website notices, these could also be communicated via an email list of subscribers.

Mission Culture

Task List:

1. Discuss and create citizen science opportunities using mission data and artifacts.
2. Contribute a success story to NASA's Office of the Chief Science Data Officer.
3. Provide feedback to the NASA open science recommendations for missions⁴⁵.
4. Use the OSF badges to recognize significant open science accomplishments of each working group on the mission team (see <https://osf.io/tvyxz/> for examples). Make these badges public on the website and related pages (e.g. code repositories, OSF project pages/subpages, etc). Wear them proudly!
5. Routinely recognize leadership in open science activities in mission-wide emails, but also include other forms of leadership and initiative.
6. Present on the efforts of the mission to incorporate and encourage Open Science practices at major meetings and venues each year.

Task Descriptions:

1. Discuss and create citizen science opportunities using mission data and artifacts.
 - a. **Why:** Citizen science opportunities may not be possible for every mission, but if so it provides a unique way for the community to contribute to the mission artifacts and science. As with other activities that incorporate community contribution, such inclusion increases the community ownership of that mission and can significantly help the mission in future proposal review processes.

⁴⁴ <https://www.cos.io/>

⁴⁵ <https://github.com/nasa/smd-open-science-guidelines>

- b. **How:** Citizen science additions generally start with a separate proposal process. See the NASA Citizen Science website⁴⁶ for many great project examples and the relevant NASA funding call for proposal instructions.
 2. Contribute a success story to NASA's Office of the Chief Science Data Officer.
 - a. **Why:** Contributing a success story for your mission that includes open science activities to NASA provides a large platform to advertise your mission on and better communicate the “wow” factor for your mission to the entire NASA community. See the NASA's [open science page](#) for current examples.
 - b. **How:** Contact the person at NASA that manages the open science page content, currently [Amanda Adams](#), with the following information and follow their instructions.
 - i. What is the topic?
 - ii. Is this NASA related, using NASA data, or being done by NASA?
 - iii. What timeline would you like to publish? If this is related to a mission with a milestone we could tie to, or something going on in the broader community that's timely (ex. Observe the Moon in Oct, hurricane season, etc.) then we typically try to tie to something broader to help us get more amplification across the agency.
 - iv. Do you have a writer that will be writing this or would we need to allocate a writer's time?
 - v. All of our stories go through a rigorous review process with a news chief and HQ PAO, which we will coordinate, this typically takes 2 weeks prior to publishing, just something to keep in mind when determining timing.
3. Provide feedback to the NASA open science recommendations for missions⁴⁷.
 - a. **Why:** Providing feedback on the NASA open science recommendations for missions is an important step towards improving those recommendations. Those responsible for those recommendations critically rely on feedback from NASA-funded missions to navigate improvements for NASA missions, and by extension provide the example to other agencies that fund observational efforts.
 - b. **How:** There are a few options to perform this work. For missions contemporary to the publication of this work, please submit a paper to this same special issue following the recommended outline and include a section describing
 - i. what Open Science activities your mission selected,
 - ii. the motivation for that selection,
 - iii. the current status of those activities, and
 - iv. how the mission benefits from those activities.

Later missions can post an issue on the GitHub repository linked in the footnote or directly email NASA's OCSDO with any comments. Make sure to include the same content outlined above in those comments in addition to suggested changes.
4. Use the OSF badges to recognize significant open science accomplishments of each working group on the mission team (see <https://osf.io/tvyxz/> for examples). Make these

⁴⁶ <https://science.nasa.gov/citizen-science/>

⁴⁷ <https://github.com/nasa/smd-open-science-guidelines>

badges public on the website and related pages (e.g. code repositories, OSF project pages/subpages, etc). Wear them proudly!

- a. **Why:** Publicly recognizing significant open science accomplishments of the individuals or working groups on the mission team rewards those individuals or groups for their efforts. Adding the relevant badges for those efforts on the person's staff landing page and ideally to their ORCID record provides additional confirmation of their achievements to others. This helps those people on their performance reviews and during the hiring process for their next employment. This activity can be done even if no internal open science competition is held for the mission team.
 - b. **How:** One way to do this is to ask the mission team members to include any open science activities in their monthly reports or otherwise notify the mission leadership of any important activities that support open science. A second method is to have a routine (e.g. 1-2 times/year) or continuous process where mission team members can nominate others or self-nominate to request one of the badges based on their activities. Leadership would then review this material and determine what activities are significant enough to warrant the award of a badge. The badge could be award to an individual or a group on the team. Once the badge is awarded, the individual or the members of the group would add their badge to their ORCID and their staff page following a predefined process.
5. Routinely recognize leadership in open science activities in mission-wide emails, but also include other forms of leadership and initiative.
- a. **Why:** Adding open science leadership alongside other forms of leadership in the mission team helps to convey the importance of open science to the mission leadership. This activity can be performed in addition to the badge and competition activities described earlier or in place of those activities if they are too complex for the mission to incorporate.
 - b. **How:** Mission leadership or an appointed person can determine what individual or group should be recognized in this way. Then, the person can email the entire mission team with a short description of the activity warranting the recognition and an applauding statement for the individual or group being recognized.
6. Present on the efforts of the mission to incorporate and encourage Open Science practices at major meetings and venues each year.
- a. **Why:** Including Open Science activities into mission presentations encourages other missions to do the same and helps shift the culture to be more open.
 - b. **How:** Add a slide to the mission presentations including an official statement from the mission about Open Science and either a short list of the Open Science activities the mission performs and why, or an example Open Science activity with a more thorough description including
 - i. the motivation for that activity,
 - ii. the current status of the activity, and
 - iii. how the mission benefits from this activity.

Additional Ideas

Task List:

1. Use recognition vocabularies such as CRediT⁴⁸ and All Contributors⁴⁹ to recognize wider contributions to data, software, and publications (see links on last slide).
2. Choose to provide higher quality metadata (e.g. better descriptions and keywords) when archiving items at a repository, whether generic or domain-specific.

Task Descriptions:

1. Use recognition vocabularies such as CRediT⁵⁰ and All Contributors⁵¹ to recognize wider contributions to data, software, and publications (see links on last slide).
 - a. **Why:** Indicating how a given co-author contributed to a given artifact provides a more accurate recognition of their contribution to the work. This can help them in performance reviews and in the hiring process for future employment. This activity also benefits the community by providing a small amount of additional information on who performs what roles on the mission team. Using the CRediT and All Contributors vocabularies to indicate these roles helps the reader understand what is meant by the role name in a standard way that relates to other works.
 - b. **How:** The CRediT vocabulary is typically used to indicate roles in a science publication. Several publishers now support the use of the CRediT vocabulary. If your selected publisher does not, please contact them. Visit the website linked below to determine what term should be associated with each co-author on the publication. Ideally, these terms will be included in a rubric used to determine author ranking for the publication so the co-author can select the term(s) most relevant to their contribution.

The All Contributors vocabulary is used similarly for software artifacts. The group has developed a software that can be integrated into a GitHub repository so that the association of the correct term to a given contribution can be seamlessly included into the pull request process.
2. Choose to provide higher quality metadata (e.g. better descriptions and keywords) when archiving items at a repository, whether generic or domain-specific.
 - a. **Why:** Including better metadata such as descriptions, keywords, and links to related resources provides the potential user with more information to find the item, determine if the item is relevant or useful, and begin to understand the proper way to use the item.
 - b. **How:** For submissions to a generic repository such as Zenodo, simply fill in more metadata fields, spend a few minutes improving the item description, and double-check that your entries are correct and all included links are not broken. For submissions to a domain-specific repository, ask for their recommendation on

⁴⁸ <https://credit.niso.org/>

⁴⁹ <https://allcontributors.org/>

⁵⁰ <https://credit.niso.org/>

⁵¹ <https://allcontributors.org/>

what additional metadata fields would be the most impactful and easiest to fill in. Then, fill them in following the instructions for each metadata field selected.